

OPTIMIZING COMMUNICATION CAPABILITIES IN NON-TERRESTRIAL NETWORKS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CONTINUOUS AND DISTRIBUTED APERTURE SOLUTIONS

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Abstract—This study explores the integration of Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) for direct-to-handheld communication, focusing on two approaches to achieve larger antenna apertures: using a single massive platform or combining smaller elements into a distributed aperture. The research compares the performance of continuous and fractionated apertures in Low Earth Orbit (LEO). The fractionated aperture, created by platforms using active Direct Radiating Arrays (DRAs), enables to reallocate resources in very narrow beams within the satellites' field of view while maintaining the same total radiating area. The study also examines the impact of grating lobes and beam separation on minimizing inter-beam interference and evaluates system capacity improvements as platform distances vary. The findings highlight the advantages of fractionated apertures for future NTN applications, particularly in enhancing system capacity for denser user populations. ¹

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper compares continuous antenna apertures with the emerging potential of distributed apertures, focusing on the innovative concept of using satellite swarms to form a vast, collaborative antenna system. As the space industry evolves, the idea of constructing a distributed antenna array from multiple satellites acting as a single, unified object is gaining traction. This concept, increasingly relevant in the context of mega-constellations, is actively being explored by research groups due to its critical importance. In the emerg-

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ing telecommunications landscape, where Direct-to-Cell (D2C) connectivity is set to integrate Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) with Terrestrial Networks (TN), distributed antenna systems could play a pivotal role. The significance of these developments is underscored by the inclusion of NTN in the 5G standardization by 3GPP with Release 17 [5], reflecting the shift towards space-based technologies in global communication infrastructures. While traditional continuous antennas have proven capabilities, they face significant challenges in large-scale deployment, as demonstrated by AST SpaceMobile's 64-meter square BlueWalker 3 experiment, which highlighted the complexity and physical limitations of such large continuous antennas [6]. Distributed antenna systems present a promising alternative by harnessing the collective capabilities of multiple smaller satellites. Missions like NASA's Nodes and Starling have provided key insights into the feasibility and benefits of such swarms. The Nodes mission, launched in December 2015, tested inter-satellite communication, autonomous command, and control without direct ground communication. Building on this, the Starling mission demonstrated significant advancements in autonomous satellite networks [7]. These missions are pivotal in the development of distributed antenna systems, highlighting the potential of satellite swarms to transform space-based communications. This paper addresses the technical challenges of distributed apertures, contributing to the discourse on the future of satellite networks, particularly for next-generation telecommunications and Earth observation systems.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In line with this concept, a swarm-based configuration seeks to create a large Radiating Element (RE) by

Fig. 1: Downlink Multibeam System Model

combining individual satellite phased arrays, ensuring that the User Terminal (UT) connects with only one element in the sky. To rigorously assess this comparison, a system model encompassing both space and user segments has been developed with the following assumptions and simplifications:

- The analysis is limited to the downlink, as the feeder uplink typically has a negligible impact on the overall forward link noise.
- Coverage is constrained by a minimum elevation angle of 25 degrees, considering potential obstructions such as buildings or mountains.
- The system operates in LEO at an altitude of 600 km, balancing orbital parameters with propagation effects. This configuration results in variable attenuation across the coverage area.

Space Segment - The space segment consists of an array of N radiating elements providing communication over a defined ground service area. A continuous aperture in LEO at 600 km supports the entire payload. The RF signal transmitted to user terminals experiences varying free space path loss during propagation. The satellite's Field of View (FoV) is the region where the User Terminal maintains Line of Sight (LOS) with the satellite at an elevation angle above 25 degrees, as per the assumptions. With this condition the satellite in the scenario has a FoV = 56° .

User Segment - A random uniform distribution of users within the satellite's FoV is generated to simulate varying user terminal densities. The distribution radius, defined by the parameter R , allows modeling of different user concentration scenarios, from low to high density. Each UT position is identified within the FoV by coordinates (θ, ϕ) , representing the signal's angle of departure from the array center to the user's position. Three different distribution are showed in Fig. 11.[3]

The phased array of N radiating elements on the satellite operates in the S band to access broader bandwidth and provide broadband direct-to-cell services. The DRA design is developed across three levels: array, subarray,

and radiating element. This setup allows each subarray to function as an orbiting platform, increasing the overall radiating surface. The elementary source is defined by a theoretical cosine diagram, given by the equation:

$$EP(\theta) = 10^{D/20} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi\theta}{2 \cdot 2\frac{\pi}{3}}\right)^n$$

with D as the Directivity of the elementary patch and n a real positive number. The choice of an elementary source let to perform a study with a good approximation of a COTS radiating component.

A Continuous Aperture consists of S radiating elements arranged in $N \times N$ subarrays, with each subarray containing $M \times M$ radiating elements. The inter-element distance is fixed at $\frac{\lambda}{2}$, where λ is the carrier signal wavelength. Beam steering is achieved through electronic and/or mechanical methods, as seen in some satellite constellations. In the S-band, a DBFN (Digitization and software-based BeamForming Network) architecture may be considered, though it is resource-intensive due to the need for constant weight updates to target fixed areas. The architecture also allows adjusting the distance between subarrays and radiating elements in terms of λ , offering flexibility to explore different aperture fractionation scenarios, which is crucial for optimizing antenna performance across various contexts. To simulate aperture fractionation, the distance d (in λ) between subarrays is varied, offering architectural flexibility as shown in the following Fig. 2:

Fig. 2: DRA Design

Fig. 3: DRA Radiation Pattern

Fig. 4: DRA 2D Radiation Pattern at $\phi = 0$

The Coordinate System depicted in Fig. 3 satisfies the following relationships:

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &= \sin(\theta_i)\cos(\phi_i) & \theta_i &= \sqrt{u_i^2 + v_i^2} \\ v_i &= \sin(\theta_i)\sin(\phi_i) & \phi_i &= \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{v_i}{u_i}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Note that there is no one-to-one relationship between (θ, ϕ) and (u, v) , since, for example, all pairs $(0, \phi)$ lead to $u=0$ and $v=0$. Nevertheless, each pair (u, v) corresponds to a unique direction of the upper half-space ($z \geq 0$).

III. SYSTEM CAPACITY ANALYSIS

The scenario analyzed involves a DRA with 900 radiating elements arranged in 5×5 subarrays, each containing 6×6 radiating elements. To estimate system capacity, it is essential to define the ground area effectively covered by the antenna signals, ensuring robust user transmission. This area is recognized as a spot beam within the satellite's coverage. According to phased array theory [1], the power radiated on Earth by a planar array can be described by the combined radiation pattern of two architectural levels: the $N \times N$ Array Factor (AF) and the $M \times M$ Subarray Factor (SAF). Since the DRA can scan the beam, we denote the scanning angle as (θ_0, ϕ_0) and use the parameter α to adjust the phase or time delay as follows:

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)\cos(\phi) - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} \sin(\theta_0)\cos(\phi_0) \right)$$

The relative radiation pattern of the two architecture levels are calculated as:

$$AF_{SA}(\theta, \phi) = \sum_{m=1}^M a_m e^{jx_m \alpha} \cdot e^{jy_m \alpha}$$

$$AF_A(\theta, \phi) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n e^{jx_n \alpha} \cdot e^{jy_n \alpha}$$

$$f(\theta, \phi) = EP(\theta) \cdot AF_{SA}(\theta, \phi) \cdot AF_A(\theta, \phi) \quad (1)$$

Defining the directivity of the system as:

$$D(\theta, \phi) = \frac{4\pi U(\theta, \phi)}{P_{rad}} \quad (2)$$

with

$$U(\theta, \phi) = |EP(\theta)|^2 \cdot |AF_{SA}(\theta, \phi)|^2 \cdot |AF_A(\theta, \phi)|^2$$

$$P_{rad} = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} U(\theta, \phi) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi$$

with a_m, a_n are the aperture amplitude distribution weights, x_m, x_n the relative distances of each RE to the reference position fixed at $x = 0$ in a reference frame as in Fig. 1.

To determine the data rate for each user, spectral efficiencies are calculated considering the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR). To ensure comparable spectral efficiencies across the coverage area, a constant power density (W/Hz) per beam is maintained. This approach achieves nearly uniform spectral efficiency by keeping the Equivalent Isotropically Radiated Power (EIRP) density consistent. The term $\left(\frac{C}{N}\right)_i^j$ denotes the carrier-to-noise ratio for $user_j$ in $beam_i$.

$$EIRP_{tot} = P_{tx} \cdot D(\theta, \phi)_{tx} = (P_{RE} \cdot N_{RE}) \cdot D(\theta, \phi)_{tx}$$

$$EIRP_{beam} = \frac{EIRP_{tot}}{N_{beam}}$$

$$EIRP_{user} = \frac{EIRP_{tot}}{N_{subBand} N_{beam}} = \frac{EIRP_{beam}}{N_{subBand}}$$

$$\left(\frac{C}{N}\right)_i^j = EIRP_{user} \cdot \left(\frac{4\pi d_j}{\lambda}\right)^{-2} \cdot \left(\frac{G}{T}\right)_j \cdot \frac{1}{kB_i^j} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- the term $P_{tx} \cdot D(\theta, \phi)_{tx}$ represents the total EIRP with P_{tx} is the power allocated to the REs, $D(\theta, \phi)_{tx}$ is the directivity of $beam_i$ toward $user_j$.
- the term $\left(\frac{4\pi d_j}{\lambda}\right)^{-2}$ represents the Free Space Path Loss that are differentiated by the term d_j such as the slant range between the satellite and $user_j$. It has value 600 km at nadir position up to a max of about 1073 km at the edge of the coverage.
- the term $\left(\frac{G}{T}\right)_j$ is the antenna gain-to-noise-temperature of the user terminal that is fixed to -20dB as first approximation.
- k the Boltzmann constant
- B_i^j the frequency bandwidth allocated to $user_j$ inside the $beam_i$.

To evaluate interference, only one polarization is considered for simplicity. The term $\left(\frac{C}{I}\right)_i^j$ represents the carrier-to-interference ratio for user $user_j$ in $beam_i$.

$$\left(\frac{C}{I}\right)_i^j = \frac{D_{tx}(\theta, \phi)_i^j}{S - D_{tx}(\theta, \phi)_i^j} \quad (4)$$

with $S = \sum_{i', i' \neq i} D_{tx}(\theta, \phi)_{i'}^j$ as the sum off all the

beams $_j$ interfering with the beam $_i$. The SINR for user $_j$ in beam $_i$ is defined by:

$$SINR_i^j = \frac{1}{\left(\left(\frac{C}{N}\right)_i^j\right)^{-1} + \left(\left(\frac{C}{I}\right)_i^j\right)^{-1}} \quad (5)$$

The final objective is to maximize overall throughput. The Total Shannon Capacity of the system is the sum of the capacities of each user terminal:

$$Capacity_{tot} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_U} B_i^j \cdot \log_2 \left(1 + SINR_i^j \right) \quad (6)$$

where N_U is the number of users.

IV. RESOURCE ALLOCATION POLICY

The Resource allocation policy is based on the definition used for spot beam. The spot beam refers to the region within the radiation pattern where the majority of the radiated power is concentrated, corresponding to the antenna's peak power output. This area is determined by

Fig. 5: Half Power Beam Width vs d_λ

the half-power beamwidth (HPBW), which represents the angular width within which the relative power is greater than 50% (or -3 dB) of the peak power in the effective radiated field. User terminals within the -3 dB area receive the strongest signals, and the HPBW is also influenced by the number of radiating elements in the antenna. Its variation with parameter d is presented in Fig. 5. In a multibeam scenario, "Null" positions — where the radiation pattern has minimal energy — can be used to distribute beams in a regular rectangular grid over the FoV, with each null serving as a potential spot beam location, due to minimal interference [2] (see Fig. 6a). In a DRA Fractionated since the AF is periodic, improper element spacing can cause grating lobes, which are periodic replicas of the main beam. The appearance of grating lobes was already illustrated for a case of Fractionated DRA with $d=20$ (λ) in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. Some grating lobes are so prominent that they reach a -10dB level from the peak, indicating significant interference for user terminals within these lobes. Furthermore, by using the same null-based beam allocation as in the Continuous DRA, beams can be positioned in nulls around the main beam to minimize interference, with grating lobes respecting the same null distribution rules

(a) Continuous

(b) Fractionated 10λ

Fig. 6: Allocation of the beams in the nulls for a DRA.

as showed in Fig. 6b. Due to so, a policy of forbidden grid points (Nulls) has been implemented in the case of DRA Fractionated as presented in Fig. 8 where for each beam allocated (O symbol), several else are forbidden (X symbol) due to grating lobes. The distance up to which grating lobe interference is considered consistent is set where a second beam's interference is less than -20 dB from first beam peak gain. For example, as shown in Fig.7, Beam 2 (orange) is positioned so that the peak interference value (blue) in direction of Beam 2 is about -26 dB from the peak in the steering direction.

Fig. 7: Optimal Beam distance disposition.

For users resource access, a Frequency Division Multiple Access (FDMA) scheme is used. A 30 MHz frequency band is divided into 9 sub-bands, each assigned to users within the beams. The 9-grid scheme allows for 9 orthogonal point grids within the FoV, where beams operate in different frequency sub-bands to avoid interference (see Fig. 12a). As the distance d between platforms increases, the grid becomes thicker (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Grid of Fractionated DRA with Grating lobes(x).

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The system capacity (in Mbps) was assessed across four scenarios: the Continuous DRA and three Fractionated DRAs with separation distances of $d = 10\lambda$, $d = 20\lambda$ and $d = 50\lambda$. 100 users were uniformly randomly distributed. Users were allocated to beams based on proximity to the beam center and interference levels below -20 dB from peak power (Fig. 12). Capacity values for different user densities are shown in Fig. 9, with Fig. 10 displaying the number of beams used in each scenario. The results indicate that:

- At $R = 100\%$, the Continuous DRA achieves the highest capacity due to the optimal arrangement of orthogonal beams. In contrast, the Fractionated DRA generates more interference as spacing d increases, due to stronger grating lobes, though all configurations use the same number of beams.
- Around $R = 30\%$, Fractionated DRA configurations with $d = 10\lambda$ and $d = 20\lambda$ offer higher capacity and use more beams compared to the Continuous DRA.
- At $R = 18\%$, as user density increases, all Fractionated DRA configurations exceed the Continuous DRA in capacity, and the number of beams allocated by the Continuous DRA starts to decrease.
- At very low R values, user density becomes so high that all users fall within a single beam, causing a sharp drop in capacity. However, the configuration with $d = 50\lambda$ at $R = 1\%$ maintains high capacity and a significant number of allocated beams, as shown in Fig. 13.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper compares a classical Continuous Directive Radiating Array (DRA) with a fractionated DRA having the same radiating surface. The results show that in high-density traffic scenarios, the fractionated DRA achieves higher system capacity. This is due to its ability to allocate more beams with narrower Half Power Beamwidths, improving frequency reuse. Future work will involve developing optimization algorithms for user-to-beam allocation as stated in [8].

Fig. 9: Capacity of the system over different Users distribution density Area

Fig. 10: Number of beams activated over different Users distribution density Area

REFERENCES

- [1] C. A. Balanis. "Antenna Theory Analysis And Design," *Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc. London*, 4th ed., 2016.
- [2] M. Pellet, G. Goussetis, J. Mota, H. Legay and F. Vidal. "Multibeam coverage optimization for broadband satellites with hybrid beamforming direct radiating arrays," in *IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation*, July 2023.
- [3] F. Vidal, H. Legay, G. Goussetis and JP. Fraysse. "Joint Precoding and Resource Allocation Strategies Applied to a Large Direct Radiating Array for GEO Telecom Satellite Applications," in *15th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, March 2021.
- [4] D. Tuzi, T. Delamotte, A. Knopp. "Beamforming Schemes for 6G Direct-to-Cell Connectivity Using Satellite Swarms," in *18th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, March 2024.
- [5] 3GPP. "Release 17." 3gpp.org. Accessed: Oct. 5, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-technologies/releases/release-17>
- [6] AST SpaceMobile. "AST SpaceMobile Achieves Space-Based 5G Cellular Broadband Connectivity From Everyday Smartphones, Another Historic World First." *ast-space.com*. Accessed: Oct. 5, 2023. [Online].
- [7] Sanchez H., McIntosh D., Cannon H., Pires C., Sullivan J., O'Connor B., D'Amico S.; "Starling1: Swarm Technology Demonstration,"; 32nd Annual Small Satellite Conference, AIAA/USU, SSC18-VII-08, Logan, UT, August 4-9 (2018)
- [8] P. Angeletti and R. De Gaudenzi, "Heuristic Radio Resource Management for Massive MIMO in Satellite Broadband Communication Networks,"; *IEEE Access*, October 2021

Fig. 11: Users distribution over the Field of view.

Fig. 12: Beams allocation with a max of 9-grids scheme for a DRA Continuous.

Fig. 13: Beams allocation with a max of 9-grids scheme in a $R_{user} = 1\%$ for different configurations.